

24DIT02 DINAMO

D4: Dataset for benchmarking automated SPM data processing routines in nanometrology

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Topography synthesis methods	3
2.1	Periodic structures	3
2.2	Atomic steps	4
2.3	Fingerprint patterns	5
2.4	Roughness	5
3	SPM error sources addition	6
4	Experimental measurements	7
5	Conclusion	8

1 Introduction

This document describes a dataset for benchmarking automated data processing methods in 24DIT02 DINAMO project, which is focusing on digital data flow and automation in dimensional nanometrology, namely when using Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM).

Based on long term experiences with real measurements on various calibration samples, the design considerations about the samples developed in the project and industrial capabilities we have created a set of synthetic data with known ground truth and known level of imperfections. This dataset is available at Zenodo platform. The data were generated using the data synthesis procedures¹ implemented in the Gwyddion open source software.² The dataset is complemented by examples of real measurements.

The intended use of synthetic data in benchmarking of SPM data processing software consists of following steps:

1. Generate ideal reference sample topography with known parameters (ground truth).
2. Distort the data by adding SPM-like error sources (noise, drift, etc).
3. Run the data processing functions under test on the data
4. Compare the results with generating parameters set in Step 1.

The dataset replaces need for running the first two steps of this procedure. However, this document also explains how they can be run with help of Gwyddion software. This is useful namely in cases when impact of some particular error source has to be studied in more detail.

The dataset is structured in a similar way as this document, providing data for different types of samples and error sources in separate directories. To view the data and to work with them, Gwyddion open source software can be used.

The dataset is available via Zenodo repository with DOI [10.5281/zenodo.17755752](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17755752)

2 Topography synthesis methods

To generate the dataset we have used various Gwyddion data synthetic modules, briefly described later in this document. The key aspect of the dataset is that the data are generated with known properties, i.e. the ground truth information is available and is accessible in each file when the “log” of the data processing operations is displayed in Gwyddion software.

2.1 Periodic structures

Periodic structures were generated using an explicit construction from nominal parameters using Gwyddion *Pattern* data synthesis module. Cartesian coordinates in the image plane (x, y) are linearly transformed to normalised coordinates (u, v) using the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/L_x & 0 \\ 0 & 1/L_y \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\phi) & \sin(\phi) \\ -\sin(\phi) & \cos(\phi) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix},$$

where ϕ is the structure orientation and L_x and L_y are the two periods of a rectangular periodic structure. For one-dimensional structures, such as gratings, we put $L_y = 1$. In coordinates (u, v) , the structure has lattice vectors $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$, so its features (bars, holes, pillars, ...) are placed at integer lattice points.

The generation proceeds image pixel by image pixel. At each pixel its real coordinates (x, y) are transformed to (u, v) . The integer parts of (u, v) determine the indices of a specific feature. Since non-ideal features may encroach upon unit squares corresponding to neighbour features, the feature corresponding to $(\lfloor u \rfloor, \lfloor v \rfloor)$ is evaluated together with all neighbours. They are combined using the $\max()$ or $\min()$ functions (depending on whether they are positive or negative) to ensure continuity in the extreme case when the features overlap.

The range of parameters estimated from real measurements for this type of reference sample was as follows: grating pitch between 100 nm and 10 μm , its height between 10 nm and 500 nm.

2.2 Atomic steps

Atomic step images were generated using an explicit construction from nominal parameters, similar as above. The ideal shapes are described by a step function of a formal coordinate u

$$s(u) = h \left\lfloor \frac{u}{d} - \frac{1}{2} \right\rfloor ,$$

where h is the step height and d is the distance between steps (terrace width). In order to obtain a specific step-like structure, Cartesian coordinates in the image plane (x, y) are transformed to the formal coordinate u in a specific manner. For an ideal amphitheatre structure centred as (x_0, y_0) , u is obtained as

$$u(x, y) = \left[(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2 \right]^{1/2} ,$$

whereas for an ideal staircase structure oriented at angle ϕ

$$u(x, y) = x \cos(\phi) + y \sin(\phi) .$$

Non-ideal structures are obtained by modifying the mapping $(x, y) \mapsto u$. For instance, an amphitheatre which has the shape of a super-ellipse instead of a circle is produced by generalising the second power to p

$$u(x, y) = \left[(x - x_0)^p + (y - y_0)^p \right]^{1/p} .$$

Moderate random deviations from the ideal shape on a large scale are realised by replacing $u(x, y)$ with

$$u(x - \delta_x, y - \delta_y) ,$$

where δ_x and δ_y two are slowly varying deformation fields, in this case different random realisations of a two-dimensional Gaussian process. Edge roughness and similar non-idealities

on a shorter scale are realised exactly in the same manner, except the added deformation fields have much shorter autocorrelation lengths. Finite step width is simulated by replacing the infinitely sharp step in $s(u)$ with a linear slope of a prescribed width.

The range of parameters estimated from real measurements for this type of reference sample was as follows: sample shape included both amphitheatres and staircases, flat area (terrace) size between 1 μm and 50 μm .

2.3 Fingerprint patterns

Stochastic data with a single dominant spatial frequency corresponding to the proposed fingerprint calibration samples were generated as solutions of a system of two couple partial differential equations. They were produced using Gwyddion *CPDE* data synthesis module. The equations have the form combining short-range positive feedback with long-range negative inhibition, known to reproduce this phenomenon and generate so-called ‘Turing patterns’. In particular, the equations

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial C_0}{\partial t} &= p_0 f(C_0) + q C_1 + \mu_0 \Delta C_0 \\ \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial t} &= q_0 f(C_1) + p C_0 + \mu_1 \Delta C_1\end{aligned}$$

were used with

$$f(u) = \frac{x}{1 + x^2/100} - \frac{x}{100}.$$

Symbol Δ represents the Laplace operator.

The simulation starts from two images C_0 and C_1 filled with random noise which determines the particular realisation of the pattern. The time evolution is then simulated using an explicit Euler-like scheme with a constant time step until the pattern converges. Periodic boundary conditions are used. In a converged state, concentrations C_0 and C_1 form the calibration images in arbitrary units. Constants p_0 , q_0 , p , q , μ_0 and μ_1 determine the convergence and resulting dominant spatial frequency. They were calibrated (together with the time step) to achieve prescribed spatial frequencies measured in pixels. The calibration relations are incorporated in the *CPDE* module. As the final step, the image is cropped to avoid periodicity and its physical dimensions in metres are set using the spatial frequency in pixels to obtain a calibration image with a known dominant spatial frequency in metres.

The range of parameters estimated from real measurements for this type of reference sample was as follows: pitch between 10 and 300 nm, feature height between 10 and 300 nm.

2.4 Roughness

Random roughness images are primarily generated using spectral synthesis using Gwyddion *Spectral* data synthesis module. In other words, the Fourier image of the rough surface is formed first. The spectral density is set to match the roughness model, in particular

$$W(k_x, k_y) = \sigma^2 \frac{T^2}{4\pi} \exp\left(-\frac{k_x^2 + k_y^2}{4} T^2\right),$$

for Gaussian roughness. The mean square roughness σ and autocorrelation length T of the roughness appear as explicit parameters in the spectral density. The spectral density determines the amplitude of the Fourier coefficient, which is its square root. The complex phase is set uniformly randomly and determines the particular realisation of the random process. A realisation of the surface is then obtained by inverse Fourier transform.

However, such image does not realistically represent a measurement of randomly rough surface with given nominal parameters. First, it is periodic. Furthermore, the root mean square roughness of the image also exactly matches the nominal value, which is not the case for real measurements rough surfaces. Even theoretically ideal realisations should have a considerable variance of parameters³ (its magnitude depends on the ratio T/L of autocorrelation length T and image size L). Further sampling considerations would be necessary for self-affine surfaces, but are generally not important for locally smooth roughness such as Gaussian. The calibration images are, therefore, obtained by cropping much larger images generated using the spectral synthesis method. Consequently, there is a realistic variation among individual calibration images and they collectively, as a set, represent a rough surface with known parameters.

The range of parameters estimated from real measurements for this type of reference sample was as follows: roughness between 50 pm and 100 nm (Sq parameter), correlation length between 5 nm and 500 nm.

3 SPM error sources addition

As this deliverable data are intended to be used for benchmarking the data processing functions performance, we have added also various error sources to the data to simulate the real measurement conditions, while keeping the ground truth information about ideal data behind.

As the number of potential combinations of different ideal datasets with error sources of different magnitude is very high, users of the dataset can also use the guidance in this document to use Gwyddion data synthesis functions to generate more combinations.

The following systematic error sources were considered when creating the dataset:

- Tip convolution effect, a distortion of measured morphology related to the fact that the SPM probe is not infinitely sharp. The resulting dataset is a convolution (mathematically, a dilation) of the probe and sample. For a known probe the effect can be simulated using algorithms presented in Ref. 4, producing simulated AFM result from ideal topographical data.
- Thermal drifts are related to thermal expansion of different microscope components before the thermal equilibrium is reached after instrument start or when the temperature in the laboratory is not sufficiently stable. They can be simulated by adding slowly varying x , y and z components to the simulated data.
- Noise in SPM data is related to the electronic circuits, mechanical vibrations and feedback loop effects. The spectral properties of noise depend on its source, like $1/f$ noise being related to light fluctuation⁵ or shot noise to detection of light beam reflected

from cantilever that is frequency independent. Often it has also some dominant frequencies, either related to the electrical sources from the power line, characteristic mechanical vibration frequencies of the tip-sample system, or acoustic noise from the environment.⁶ For simple simulations independent noise in each pixel can be sufficient. Correlated noise with given power spectrum is generated using spectral synthesis,⁷ i.e. constructing the Fourier coefficients with given magnitudes and random phases and using the inverse fast Fourier transform (FFT) to obtain the correlated noise. A special type of noise related to the feedback loop effects are scars/strokes, short segments of the scanned line that are not following the surface.

- Line noise (line mismatch) causes shifts between individual lines scanned in the fast scanning axis that form the image. The source of this noise is not very well understood, but most probably it is a mixture of low frequency noise, drift, impact of changing the tip motion direction, and impact of tiny changes of the tip behaviour (contamination, tip wear, etc.).
- Interference of light which misses cantilever and is reflected off the sample surface towards the beam deflection detector can generate visible fringe pattern on the sample.^{8,9} In the simplest approximation this error source can be expressed as a harmonic function of the height.
- Feedback loop effects are related to undershoots and overshoots of the proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller that is used to keep the probe-sample interaction constant via z motion of the tip or sample. These can be simulated for synthetic data by establishing a virtual feedback loop based on a model force-distance dependence and calculating the cantilever response using a suitable model, e.g. damped harmonic oscillator for tapping mode measurements¹⁰ combined with modelling the time evolution of the feedback loop response.

When creating a dataset, the following error parameters ranges were used: tip radius for a spherical tip apex was used, up to 20 nm. Noise levels included random noise up to 2 nm (RMS), line mismatch up to 2 nm and periodic noise with 2-50 periods per line and amplitude up to 1 nm. Polynomial background, drift and feedback loop effects were treated individually for each type of structure.

4 Experimental measurements

To provide real world examples of metrologically relevant SPM data, measurements of typical metrology samples covered by the project (gratings, self-assembled structure, silicon steps) are provided in the dataset. These were obtained using Dimension Icon microscope (Bruker) at Czech Metrology Institute and using custom-built metrological SPM. Data were collected in either tapping mode or in PeakForceQNM mode. Measurements were performed on commercial gratings, PTB crystalline sample and INRIM self-assembled sample. Data that were non-ideal, typically showing some line mismatch noise, polynomial background or tip-sample interference are also included, to make the validation of routines in

non-ideal conditions possible. Therefore the experimental data in this deliverable do not represent the best measurement capabilities of the used equipment. The goal was the opposite, to provide real world non-ideal data that someone would still like to use for calibration purposes.

5 Conclusion

The dataset includes generated and measured topography data designed for benchmarking data processing routines in SPM. While it already includes wide range of error sources applied on the ideal topographies, the presented methods can be also used to generate synthetic data when some particular error source has to be studied more in detail or when the experimental measurements show that some error sources parameters lie outside of the ranges expected here.

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